
Exploring a Non-linear World Through Computation

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DECLARATION

I affirm that I have identified all my sources and that no part of my dissertation paper uses unacknowledged materials.

ABSTRACT

This work explores non-linear dynamics in terms of discrete and continuous systems. For discrete systems, the logistic map displays period-doubling paths to chaos, measured in terms of Lyapunov exponents and fractal bifurcation diagrams. For continuous systems, linear stability analysis and bifurcation theory exhibit equilibrium behavior changes, as found with saddle-node and Hopf bifurcations in differential equations. Gravitational systems employ these methodologies for the three-body problem, with Lagrange points—found using Jacobi coordinates—providing equilibrium solutions. Stability analysis demonstrates L_1, L_2, L_3 , the collinear points are highly unstable. L_4 and L_5 , the hilltops are highly stable points, which, stabilize through coriolis forces, and harbor Trojan asteroids. Numerical modeling points to chaotic orbital behavior in perturbed gravity laws or extreme perturbations. Combining Poincaré maps, we unravel chaotic trajectories in such systems as the Hénon-Heiles model. From theory to computation, this paper highlights universal non-linear effects from population models to celestial mechanics and offers predictors for stability in complicated systems.

Keywords: Chaos, Bifurcations, Logistic map, Lagrange points, Three-body problem.

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1 Introduction

Non-linear dynamics (NLD) is the basis of comprehension of complex natural systems in which interactions are never linear and tend to produce phenomena like chaos, bifurcations, and emergent patterns. From population growth models to celestial mechanics, non-linear systems resist trivial linear approximations and require strong analytical and computational tools. This research delves into the complex realm of non-linear dynamics, taking three of the most significant fields: discrete one-dimensional maps (represented by the logistic map), Poincaré maps (focus being on Lorenz Attractor and the Hénon-Heiles System), and continuous gravitational systems (the focus being on the three-body problem). In connecting theoretical backdrops to numerical simulations, the research sheds light on how systems ranging from biological populations to planetary orbits are regulated by non-linear behavior.

Non-linear dynamics, NLD, in the form that we recognize it today, owes its origins to the early work of Henri Poincaré in the late 19th century. In the course of a study of the three-body problem, Poincaré found that even deterministic systems could display extremely random behavior, the first indications of what has come to be known as chaos theory [14]. These underlying concepts of stability were later formalized by Lyapunov with his stability criteria for motion [15]. During the 20th century, the invention of discrete maps, in particular the logistic map popularized by Robert May [16], demonstrated how nonlinear equations of simple complexity could produce complex and chaotic dynamics by period-doubling bifurcations. The Lorenz system, developed by Edward Lorenz in 1963 during the modeling of atmospheric convection, also yielded one of the earliest known instances of a strange attractor, further stimulating research into chaotic systems [17]. The Hénon–Heiles system, also described in 1964 for the investigation of stellar motion within galaxies, gave another paradigmatic model of chaotic trajectories [18].

In gravitational dynamics, the three-body problem has been the central historical actor. The issue was initially described by Newton in the *Principia Mathematica* (1687) [22], but true analytical advances had to wait till the 18th century. Euler and Lagrange determined particular solutions for simplified cases when bodies are arranged to form equilateral triangles or aligned configurations [19, 20]. Specific configurations gave way to the solution of equilibrium positions, now designated as Lagrange points. The rigor-

ous treatment of their stability and dynamics led to contemporary celestial mechanics. During the 20th century, Hill's lunar motion work [21] and Szebehely's comprehensive treatment of the restricted three-body problem [7] extended the knowledge of these points and their position in gravitational systems.

The project evolves from basic concepts towards advanced applications:

- **Foundations of Non-Linear Dynamics:** We start with the study of one- and two-dimensional continuous systems, examining fixed points, linear stability, and bifurcations (saddle-node, transcritical, pitchfork, and Hopf).
- **Discrete Systems and Chaos:** The logistic map is discussed to show period-doubling cascades, Lyapunov exponents, and chaos. Cobweb diagrams and bifurcation plots show the emergence of chaos from order.
- **Celestial Mechanics:** The three-body problem is placed within the context of gravitational dynamics. In Jacobi coordinates and Poincaré maps, we study the restricted three-body problem and find the Lagrange points, assessing their stability via linearization and eigenvalue analysis.

The report concludes by weaving these strands together to emphasize applications in astrophysics, including orbital stability and chaotic orbits in multi-body systems. Through the combination of analytical derivations and Python-based simulations, this work bridges theory and computation, providing insights into the unpredictable yet patterned nature of non-linear worlds.

After this introduction, the report explores methods of analyzing continuous systems (sections 3, 4, 5), discrete maps (section 6), and gravitational problems (section 7). Each chapter progresses toward the study of chaos and stability, ending with the treatment of Lagrange points and their contribution to celestial mechanics. The conclusion (Chapter 8) looks at wider implications, from astrophysical events to future studies in accretion discs and black holes.

2 Non-Linear Dynamics - The essence of this study

We want to begin with a brief introduction to non-linear system dynamics, [1]. As we know, dynamics is the study of the evolution of systems over time. Looking back at Newton's second law, all motion is governed by the force equation:

$$F = m\vec{a} \quad \text{or} \quad \vec{F} = m \frac{d^2 \vec{x}}{dt^2}$$

This is a rather simplistic, linearized approach to studying dynamic systems. However, real-life systems are rarely linear; they are rather complex and chaotic and cannot be accurately studied by solely considering Newton's second law. Hence, the need arises for a more robust approach that helps us better understand the systems around us. While linear systems do not account for non-linearity, non-linear systems, on the other hand, do. Examples of non-linear systems:

- Logistic Equation (Population Growth Model)
- Three-Body Problem
- Mechanical Oscillators

SDIC (Sensitive Dependence on Initial Conditions) is a defining component of chaos and chaotic systems. Even tiny changes in the initial conditions can drastically alter the system's behavior. This phenomenon is found only in deterministic systems (systems that evolve in the same way every time) and not in random systems. In non-linear dynamics, we observe the evolution of systems with respect to time in the phase space; a mathematical space where each point represents a state of the dynamic system. For this section, our study will be divided primarily into two parts:

- One dealing with continuous systems
- The other with discrete systems

Although there aren't major changes to the main formulations for these two system types, we will observe some slight modifications and adjustments in the upcoming sections.

3 One Dimensional Continuous Systems

Continuous systems are characterized by differential equations that show the position of the test particle and its evolution with time. One-dimensional continuous systems deal with first-order differential equations, and two-dimensional continuous systems deal with second-order differential equations. We first consider a one-dimensional system of the type $\dot{x} = f(x)$, where x is a function of time and $f(x)$ is a function of x [1].

3.1 Phase Portraits

Imagine a fluid that is flowing, we call this phase fluid. We use a test particle, called phase point, and see how it flows in the fluid, over time. The particle follows the function $\dot{x} = f(x)$, where x is the position of the particle, which evolves with time. If we place the particle at an initial point of x_0 , we can trace out the trajectories followed by the particle in time, which so happens to be the solution of the differential equation. The different trajectories followed by the particle is known as the phase portrait. Let us see the phase portrait of the system $\dot{x} = x(1 - x)$, as an example of what phase portrait is.

Figure 1: Phase Portrait of the function $\dot{x} = x(1 - x)$.

3.2 Fixed Points

The fixed points are points where, the value of x^* is, $f(x^*) = 0$. These points are where the system doesn't change with time, i.e., x remains constant. Such points represent equilibrium solutions. An equilibrium is defined to be stable if all perturbations near it damp out in time, hence, stable fixed points represent equilibrium positions.

Figure 2: Diagram to visualise fixed points. Here, $\dot{x} = \sin(x)$. [1]

- Here, 0 is a fixed point. At $\dot{x} = 0$, there is no flow.
- The solid black dots here show the stable fixed points, also know as attractors, as the flow is towards them.
- The hollow dots represent unstable fixed points as the flow is away from them. They are also called repellors.

3.3 Linear Stability Analysis

This is a crucial step for understanding the stability of a fixed point and is done by linearizing about a fixed point. We consider x^* to be a fixed point. $\eta(t) = x(t) - x^*$, is a small disturbance from x^* . To determine the rate of the disturbance, we differentiate it as:-

$$\dot{\eta} = \frac{d}{dt}(x - x^*) = x^*$$

Therefore, $\dot{\eta} = \dot{x} = f(x) = f(x^* + \eta)$.

Using Taylor expansion, we have

$$f(x^* + \eta) = f(x^*) + \eta f'(x^*) + O(\eta^2) \tag{1}$$

$f(x^*) = 0$, as it is a fixed point and $O(\eta^2)$, represents all quadratic terms. Therefore, eqn 1 becomes,

$$\dot{\eta} = \eta f'(x^*) + O(\eta^2) \quad (2)$$

if, $f'(x^*) \neq 0$, the $O(\eta^2)$ terms are negligible and the approximation becomes :-

$$\dot{\eta} = \eta f'(x^*) \quad (3)$$

Thus eqn 3, is the linearization about x^* . What can we infer from eqn 3?

- if $f'(x^*) > 0$, the perturbation grows exponentially.
- if $f'(x^*) < 0$, the perturbation decays exponentially.
- if $f'(x^*) = 0$, the $O(\eta^2)$ terms are present and we require a non-linear analysis.
- the magnitude of the slope of $f'(x^*)$ gives us how stable a point is and the sign shows us what type of a fixed point it is.

3.4 Bifurcations

The qualitative changes in the dynamics of a system with respect to its parameter are called *bifurcations*. These represent sudden transitions in the dynamic systems. The topological structure of the phase portrait changes as the parameter is varied. The four most common types of bifurcations are:-

- Saddle Node Bifurcations
- Transcritical Bifurcations
- Pitchfork Bifurcations
- Hopf Bifurcations

3.4.1 Saddle Node Bifurcations

The most basic mechanism by which fixed points are created and then they mutually destroy one another. As we vary the parameter, saddle points are created, they collide and then destroy each other. The most common example is-

$$\dot{x} = r + x^2 \quad (4)$$

where, r is the parameter which we are varying.

Figure 3: Figure to show the stability of fixed points. [1]

General discussion :- referring to figure 3

- When r is negative, we have two fixed points; one is stable and the other is unstable.
- When $r = 0$, we have the semi-stable fixed point at the origin.
- When r is positive, we have no fixed points whatsoever.

3.4.2 Transcritical Bifurcations

An indestructible fixed point. Such a fixed point can never be destroyed no matter how the parameter is varied. But the type of stability of the fixed point might just change. The normal form of the bifurcation is-

$$\dot{x} = rx - x^2 \tag{5}$$

here, both x and r can have negative or positive values.

Figure 4: Figure to showcase the stability points. [1]

General discussion :- referring to figure 4

- $x^* = 0$, for all values of r (fixed point) and another fixed point is at $x = r$

- Stability Swap:-
 - When $r < 0$, $x = 0$ is stable and $x = r$ is unstable
 - When $r > 0$, $x = 0$ is unstable and $x = r$ is stable

We can conclude that the stability swaps when r crosses 0.

3.4.3 Pitchfork Bifurcations

This is found mainly with systems that have a certain symmetry. Here, the fixed points appear in pairs and get destroyed in pairs as well. The standard equation is -

$$\dot{x} = rx - x^3 \tag{6}$$

where r is the constant parameter. The fixed points for this are:- $x^* = 0$ and $x^* = \pm\sqrt{r}$. $r < 0$ is the only fixed point at $x = 0$ and when $r > 0$, we have 3 fixed points at, $x = 0$ and $x = \pm\sqrt{r}$. Hence, we see a stability swap for this as well. The 2 main divisions of the pitchfork bifurcations are -

- Supercritical Pitchfork Bifurcation:
 - When $r < 0$ we have a single stable point at $x = 0$.
 - When $r = 0$, the stable fixed point is at the origin, but it starts losing its stability due to loss of the linearization term, but that happens very slowly. This phenomenon is known as critically slowing down.
 - As r increases, the two fixed points emerge symmetrically because the stability of $x = 0$ changes. (The two black dots show the fixed point in fig 5).

Figure 5: Shows supercritical bifurcation as r changes. [1]

- Subcritical Pitchfork Bifurcation:

- here, the cubic term destabilizes the system instead of stabilizing it. Hence, the equation now becomes

$$\dot{x} = rx + x^3 \tag{7}$$

Since the cubic term here has a destabilizing effect, it helps the fixed points to blow up completely to infinity.

3.4.4 Hopf Bifurcations

We shall discuss this while doing the two-dimensional continuous systems, since it is more widely used there. (Discussed in section [5.4.3](#).)

4 Lorenz Trick

Before we jump ship and hop onto the continuous systems in two dimensions, we would like to discuss a very useful trick known as the Lorenz Trick [1]. This trick basically helps us to convert a higher order differential equation, (here, we take the example of a third order differential equation) into a system of first order ordinary differential equations. Any third order differential equation can be written as,

$$\frac{d^3x}{dt^3} = f\left(x, \frac{dx}{dt}, \frac{d^2x}{dt^2}, t\right).$$

This can be transformed by introducing new variables,

$$y = \frac{dx}{dt}, \quad z = \frac{d^2x}{dt^2}$$

Therefore, the third order ordinary differential equation can now be written as three first order ordinary differential equations,

$$\begin{aligned}\frac{dx}{dt} &= y \\ \frac{dy}{dt} &= z \\ \frac{dz}{dt} &= f(x, y, z, t)\end{aligned}$$

In the Lorenz system itself, we use this trick. This approach works on systems whose attractors are almost flat, that is, two-dimensional. It involves smart rescalings, rearranging physical equations and change of variables to get to the most famous Lorenz equations. The Lorenz system is given by:

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{x} &= \sigma(y - x), \\ \dot{y} &= x(\rho - z) - y, \\ \dot{z} &= xy - \beta z,\end{aligned}$$

where σ , ρ , and β are parameters. We have extensively discussed the Lorenz system later in section 5.5.3. This transformation, of changing higher order differential equations into simple systems which are easier to analyse is the Lorenz trick, and it is used widely in dynamical systems analysis. It helps us to bring the system to a first order system, which is easier to analyse in the phase space geometrically.

5 Two-Dimensional Continuous Systems

5.1 Linear Systems

Till now, our discussion was limited to one-dimensional systems . Now we start looking at two-dimensional systems [1]. A two-dimensional linear system is of the form:-

$$\dot{x} = ax + by, \quad \dot{y} = cx + dy \quad (8)$$

here, a, b, c, d are the constant parameters. This can be written in the vector form as - $\vec{\dot{x}} = A\vec{x}$ where, $A = \begin{pmatrix} a & b \\ c & d \end{pmatrix}$ and $\vec{x} = \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix}$. The solutions of $\vec{\dot{x}} = A\vec{x}$ can be plotted easily in the phase plane.

We now, take the help of the simple harmonic pendulum. As we know its equation of motion is of the form:-

$$m\ddot{x} + kx = 0 \quad (9)$$

where m is the mass and k is the spring constant. To find the motion of the system without actually solving it, we can deduce the phase plane for this system and hence, find the solutions. To find the vector field, we need to have the state of the system, which is given by the position vector \vec{x} and velocity vector \vec{v} . We use a trick called the Lorenz trick (section 4), described before, to help us model the second order differential equation to the first order. Therefore, we write eqn 9 in the form,

$$\dot{x} = v, \quad \dot{y} = -\frac{k}{m}x \quad (10)$$

We know that $\nu^2 = k/m$. Hence, eqn 10 becomes,

$$\dot{x} = v, \quad \dot{v} = -\nu^2x \quad (11)$$

Therefore, the system assigns a vector $(\vec{\dot{x}}, \vec{\dot{v}}) = (v, -\nu^2x)$ at each point of (x, v) on the phase plane. For positive x the vectors point vertically downwards, and for negative x , they point vertically upwards.

Figure 6: Vector field for simple harmonic motion. [Drive link for the code.](#)

The origin is a fixed point, as $(\dot{x}, \dot{v}) = (0, 0)$. The fixed point corresponds to the point of static equilibrium in the phase space, the mass is at rest at this position. A phase point that starts from any starting point will circulate around the origin and eventually return to its starting point. These form the closed orbits, which correspond to the periodic motions. fig 7 shows this as a phase portrait. When x is negative, the velocity, v is 0, which corresponds to an extreme position.

Figure 7: Phase portrait of the simple harmonic motion. [1]

5.1.1 Classifying the Linear Systems and Some Notes on Fixed Points

Let us consider a trajectory of the form,

$$\mathbf{x} = e^{\lambda t} \mathbf{v}. \quad (12)$$

Here, \mathbf{v} is some vector and λ is the growth rate. To find a suitable form of the equation, we substitute eqn 12 into eqn 5.1 and finally obtain the well-known form -

$$A\mathbf{v} = \lambda\mathbf{v} \quad (13)$$

which is the eigenvalue equation. Here, \mathbf{A} is the eigenvector and λ is the eigenvalue. This eqn 12 will have 2 eigenvalues λ_1 and λ_2 . Therefore, the solution is,

$$x(t) = c_1 e^{\lambda_1 t} \mathbf{v}_1 + c_2 e^{\lambda_2 t} \mathbf{v}_2 \quad (14)$$

This is the general solution and is a linear combination of all solutions to eqn 5.1.

Some Notes on Fixed Points

The eigenvalues are

$$\lambda_{1,2} = \frac{1}{2} \left(\tau \pm \sqrt{\tau^2 - 4\Delta} \right) \quad (15)$$

here, τ is the trace of the matrix A and Δ is the determinant. According to eigenvalue properties, we can have, $\Delta = \lambda_1 \lambda_2$ and $\tau = \lambda_1 + \lambda_2$.

- If $\Delta < 0$, the eigenvalues are real and have opposite signs. The fixed point is a saddle point in this case.
- If $\Delta > 0$, the eigenvalues in this case are either real and have same signs; then they form nodes or if they are complex conjugates, then they form spirals and centers. Nodes will satisfy $\tau^2 - 4\Delta > 0$ and spiral will satisfy $\tau^2 - 4\Delta < 0$. $\tau^2 - 4\Delta = 0$ is the separation between nodes and spirals. Eigenvalues, in this case, are purely imaginary. The stability depends on τ .
 - $\tau < 0$ both eigenvalues are negative; hence they are stable.
 - $\tau > 0$, the eigenvalues have positive real parts and hence the fixed points are unstable.
- If $\Delta = 0$, at least one eigenvalue for this is 0. This shows that the origin is not an

isolated fixed point; it is either a whole line or a whole plane of fixed points.

- Centers (fixed points where trajectories form the closed orbits around the equilibrium point), stars (fixed points where trajectories radiate outward or inward), and degenerate nodes (only one linearly dependent eigenvector) are all borderline cases.
- If $Re(\lambda) \neq 0$ for any eigenvalues, we have hyperbolic fixed point. They give us a sense of the structural stability of the phase plane.

Figure 8: Figure to visualise the fixed point classifications. [1]

5.2 Linearization for 2-D Systems

We now try to replicate our linearization technique developed in section 3.3 for two-dimensional linear systems. Consider the system-

$$\dot{x} = f(x, y) \text{ and } \dot{y} = g(x, y) \quad (16)$$

Let us consider (x^*, y^*) as the fixed point. Hence, $f(x^*, y^*) = 0$ and $g(x^*, y^*) = 0$. Let, $u = x - x^*$ and $v = y - y^*$ denote the small perturbations from the fixed point. Much like we did earlier, to determine the rate of decay or growth of the disturbance, we derive the differential equations. For u we have-

$$\dot{u} = \dot{x} \quad (17)$$

$$= f(x^+u, y^*v) \quad (18)$$

$$= f(x^*, y^*) + u \frac{\delta f}{\delta x} + v \frac{\delta f}{\delta y} + O(u^2, v^2, uv) \quad [\text{from Taylor expansion}] \quad (19)$$

here $O(u, v)$ denotes the quadratic terms present and are extremely small. As we know already $f(x^*, y^*) = 0$, therefore the equation further simplifies to -

$$\dot{u} = u \frac{\delta f}{\delta x} + v \frac{\delta f}{\delta y} + O(u^2, v^2, uv). \quad (20)$$

Similarly for v ; we have

$$\dot{v} = u \frac{\delta g}{\delta x} + v \frac{\delta g}{\delta y} + O(u^2, v^2, uv) \quad (21)$$

Hence, the disturbance $[(u, v)]$ evolution can now be reduced to the form -

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{u} \\ \dot{v} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\delta f}{\delta x} & \frac{\delta f}{\delta y} \\ \frac{\delta g}{\delta x} & \frac{\delta g}{\delta y} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} + \text{quadratic terms} \quad (22)$$

Here, the matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\delta f}{\delta x} & \frac{\delta f}{\delta y} \\ \frac{\delta g}{\delta x} & \frac{\delta g}{\delta y} \end{pmatrix} \quad (23)$$

is called the Jacobian matrix, at the fixed point $f(x^*, y^*)$. We can neglect the quadratic terms as they are very small and insignificant in eqn 22. Hence, our linearized system is now,

$$\begin{pmatrix} \dot{u} \\ \dot{v} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{\delta f}{\delta x} & \frac{\delta f}{\delta y} \\ \frac{\delta g}{\delta x} & \frac{\delta g}{\delta y} \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} u \\ v \end{pmatrix} \quad (24)$$

Can we really ignore the quadratic terms?

Yes we can. As long as the fixed point is not part of the borderline cases. This is because the borderline cases can get altered by even the smallest of disturbances and non-linear terms.

5.2.1 Classifying Fixed points based on Stability

Refer to section 5.1.1 for a note on fixed points.

- Stars and degenerate nodes are very unstable and get affected by the tiniest of disturbance in the non-linear terms. But, centers are very stable; their stability doesn't change, even though they are part of the borderline cases.
- Repellers (sources): both eigenvalues have positive and real parts.
- Attractors (sinks): both eigenvalues have negative and real parts.
- Saddles: one value is positive and one is negative.

5.3 Limit cycles

A limit cycle is defined as an isolated closed trajectory, isolated meaning the trajectories are not closed; they spiral away or toward the limit cycle.

Figure 9: Different types of limit cycles. [1]

A limit cycle is called stable when all the trajectories approach the cycle. Otherwise, we say that the limit cycle is unstable. Stable limit cycle model systems with self-sustained oscillations. We shall use the concept of limit cycles to study different bifurcations.

5.4 Types of Bifurcations

The definition of bifurcations has already been discussed in section 3.4. There is no major change just because more dimensions have been added. All the drama is confined to the one-dimensional subspace, while the rest of the system flows in the other dimensions.

5.4.1 Saddle-Node Bifurcation

As we already know, fixed points are created and destroyed as part of the saddle node bifurcation. The normal form in two-dimensions is,

$$\dot{x} = \mu - x^2, \quad \dot{y} = -y \quad (25)$$

In the x-direction, the behavior is the same as discussed in section 3.4.1. For the y-direction, the phase portrait changes as μ is varied.

General Discussion-

- At $\mu > 0$ there are two fixed points; which are a stable node at $(x^*, y^*) = (\sqrt{\mu}, 0)$ and a saddle at $(-\sqrt{\mu}, 0)$.
- As μ decreases, the 2 fixed points approach each other and dissociate one and the other.
- When $\mu < 0$ they disappear.

Figure 10: Schematic representation of bifurcation points for saddle node. [1]

Even after the points have destroyed each other, they leave a *ghost*. There is a bottleneck region created that sucks the trajectories in and delays their passage before letting them out the other side.

Figure 11: Highlights the bottleneck region. [1]

5.4.2 Transcritical and Pitchfork Bifurcations

We have already discussed them in sections 3.4.2 and 3.4.3. For the x-direction, the analysis remains the same as in the previous sections, and for the y direction, the motion

now becomes exponentially damped. Hence, we get the following equations.

For transcritical bifurcations we have-

$$\dot{x} = \mu x - x^2, \quad \dot{y} = -y \tag{26}$$

For supercritical pitchfork bifurcations we have-

$$\dot{x} = \mu x - x^3, \quad \dot{y} = -y \tag{27}$$

For subcritical pitchfork bifurcations we have-

$$\dot{x} = \mu x + x^3, \quad \dot{y} = -y \tag{28}$$

The analysis for each remains the same as is discussed in sections [3.4.2](#) and [3.4.3](#).

5.4.3 Hopf Bifurcations

Our main area of interest for two-dimensional bifurcations. The stability for fixed points is completely dependent on the eigenvalues. If they are imaginary, they are very stable, and if they are real, they are unstable. As soon as a fixed point enters from the imaginary plane to the real plane, they destabilize, as the parameter μ varies.

Supercritical Hopf Bifurcation

This occurs when a stable spiral changes into an unstable spiral. This is surrounded by a nearly elliptical limit cycle. The canonical form of the supercritical bifurcation is-

$$\dot{r} = \mu r - r^3 \tag{29}$$

$$\dot{\theta} = \omega + br^2 \tag{30}$$

Here, μ is a parameter that measures the stability of the fixed point at the origin; ω is the frequency of the oscillations, and b determines the dependence of frequency on amplitude. Below are a few phase portraits for different values of μ .

Figure 12: Supercritical Hopf bifurcations. [1]

- When $\mu < 0$, $r=0$ and we have a stable spiral whose sense of rotation depends on ω .
- When $\mu = 0$, the origin is a stable, yet spiral is weak and decay happens extremely fast.
- For $\mu > 0$, the origin is now unstable, and a stable circular limit cycle is formed (in the ideal case, actually an elliptical limit cycle is formed) at $r=\sqrt{\mu}$.

From the phase portraits we can deduce the nature of the eigenvalues. The eigenvalues cross from the imaginary axis (stability) to the real axis (instability) as μ increases. This is also proved mathematically.

Subcritical Hopf Bifurcation

The canonical equations for this case are

$$\dot{r} = \mu r + r^3 - r^5 \tag{31}$$

$$\dot{\theta} = \omega + br^2 \tag{32}$$

The r^3 term is the dangerous term! It destabilizes the limit cycle and pushes the trajectories out of the origin.

Figure 13: Phase portraits of subcritical Hopf bifurcation. [1]

- When $\mu < 0$, there are two attractors here, and there is a stable limit cycle and a stable fixed point at the origin, as in the earlier case. But here, we also have an extra, unstable limit cycle between them.
- When $\mu = 0$, this is where the subcritical Hopf bifurcation takes place. The origin becomes unstable in this case. This happens because as μ increases, the unstable cycle encompasses the fixed point at the origin and makes it unstable.
- For $\mu > 0$, only the unstable large amplitude limit cycle is present, and all solutions now are forced to divulge towards the large amplitude cycle. This shows that the system shows hysteresis. Large amplitude oscillations cannot be eliminated by taking $\mu = 0$. The oscillations are present till $\mu = -\frac{1}{4}$. At this juncture, the stable and unstable limit cycle collide to destroy each other.

5.5 Poincaré Maps

This is a very powerful tool in the formulation of non-linear dynamics. They show how a trajectory intersects a given section at regular intervals. Rather than graphing the continuous change of a system, a Poincaré map only traces out the points at which the trajectory intersects a selected section of phase space, this selected section is called the Poincaré sections. This maps a high-dimensional system onto a lower-dimensional representation in which patterns become easier to observe.

Figure 14: Poincaré map schematic; here the Poincare section is denoted by S . [1]

If a Poincaré map (P) is defined as : here \mathbf{x}_k denotes the k th intersection at the Poincaré section. If \mathbf{x}^* is a fixed point of P , meaning $P(\mathbf{x}^*) = \mathbf{x}^*$. This means that a trajectory starting at \mathbf{x}^* will return to \mathbf{x}^* after some time and hence forms a closed orbit of the system. By looking at the behavior of this trajectory in the Poincaré section, we can deduce the stability of closed orbits concerning Poincaré maps.

Types of Orbits in Poincare Maps

If we plot any Poincaré maps, we will be able to see these type of orbits.

- **Periodic orbits:** Periodic motion is characterized by a finite number of discrete points. These points return to the same coordinates in the phase space over time.
- **Quasi-periodic orbits:** They form closed curves in the Poincare sections. They show a non-repeating but stable motion.
- **Chaotic orbits:** They show unpredictable behaviour, and there are scattered points throughout the phase space.

5.5.1 The Stability of Periodic Orbits

In this part, we will be analyzing whether the fixed point and closed orbit are at all stable. Let v_0 be an extremely small perturbation such that $\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{v}_0$ is in the Poincare section S . Hence, after the first return to S , we have,

$$\mathbf{x} + \mathbf{v}_0 = P(\mathbf{x}^* + \mathbf{v}_0) \quad (33)$$

$$= P(\mathbf{x}^*) + [DP(\mathbf{x}^*)]v_0 + O(\|\mathbf{v}_0\|^2) \quad (34)$$

here, $O(\|\mathbf{v}_0\|^2)$ are the negligible small quadratic terms and $DP(\mathbf{x}^*)$, is a $(n-1) \times (n-1)$ matrix, known as the linearized Poincaré map. As, $\mathbf{x}^* = P(\mathbf{x}^*)$ eqn 34 becomes,

$$\mathbf{v}_1 = [DP(\mathbf{x}^*)]\mathbf{v}_0 \quad (35)$$

Thus, we can summarize the criteria as, "the closed orbits are only stable if and only if $|\lambda_j| < 1$ for $j = 1$ to $(n-1)$ ". Here, $|\lambda_j|$ are the eigenvalues of the $DP(\mathbf{x}^*)$ matrix.

5.5.2 Henon Heiles System- as an application of Poincaré maps

This is an example of a non-linear system in celestial mechanics. It describes the motion of stars in two-dimensional galactic potential. The Hamiltonian is given as-

$$H = \frac{1}{2}(p_x^2 + p_y^2) + \frac{1}{2}(x^2 + y^2) + x^2y - \frac{1}{3}y^3 \quad (36)$$

The equations of motion are:-

$$\dot{x} = p_x, \quad \dot{y} = p_y \quad (37)$$

$$\dot{p}_x = -x - 2xy, \quad \dot{p}_y = -y - x^2 + y^2 \quad (38)$$

Here, we develop the Poincaré map by recording the positions and momenta whenever the trajectory crosses a given Poincaré section in the phase space. In easily integrable portions, we can see smooth curves, otherwise, we can only see scattered points, which reveal chaos. This helps us visualize the system more clearly. When the total energy is low, we see stable orbits. As the energy increases, we start to see chaotic trajectories.

Figure 15: Poincare map of the Henon-Heiles System. [Drive link for the code.](#)

5.5.3 Lorenz Attractor

The three coupled equations are :-

$$\dot{x} = \sigma(y - x) \quad (39)$$

$$\dot{y} = x(\rho - z) - y \quad (40)$$

$$\dot{z} = xy - \beta z \quad (41)$$

here, x represents fluid convection, y represents temperature difference, and z represents the vertical motion or atmospheric energy. σ is the Prandtl number which controls the fluid viscosity, ρ is the Rayleigh number controls the behavior of the system and β is the geometric factor related to the system size.

This system exhibits SDIC (Sensitive Dependence on Initial Conditions) exceptionally well. The trajectory of the Lorenz attractor's phase space shows very complicated trajectories, which form two lobes, but they never repeat and show extreme chaotic behavior. This is now called a strange attractor. The famous "Butterfly effect", came from the Lorenz attractor itself. Primarily, it has a variety of applications in weather dynamics.

Lorenz System

Figure 16: The Lorenz System. The two lobes can be seen here very clearly. [Drive link for the code.](#)

6 One-Dimensional Discrete Maps

Discrete maps show time evolution in very small discrete steps, unlike differential equations, which show it continuously and instantaneously over time. Discrete systems are described by iterative maps [1]. They are usually of the form $x_{(n+1)} = f(x_n)$, where the function $f(x)$ maps the current state x_n to its next state $x_{(n+1)}$. The fixed points are solutions to these equations. We can examine the derivation of the fixed point to understand whether it is stable. Let's say, $\lambda = f'(x^*)$, now let us examine different limits of λ -

- if $|\lambda| < 1$, the fixed point is attracting (stable),
- if $|\lambda| > 1$, the fixed point is repelling (unstable),
- if $|\lambda| = 1$, we need a higher order analysis.

6.1 Cobweb Diagrams

To graphically visualise the behaviour of iterative maps, we use cobweb diagrams, which also helps us to understand the analysis of fixed points. The cobweb diagram for the cosine map is,

Figure 17: Cobweb diagram for cosine map. [Drive link for the code.](#)

If the trajectory spirals towards the fixed point it is stable; if it diverges, it is unstable; and if it oscillates it is periodic and chaotic.

6.2 Bifurcations in One-Dimensional Maps

The essence of bifurcations remains the same as discussed in section 3.4. Here, we would just give an overview-

- **Saddle Node Bifurcations:-** Two stable points are created; one is stable and the other is unstable. They eventually merge and destroy each other.
- **Period-Doubling Bifurcations:** A stable fixed point emerges and becomes unstable and a stable cycle-two emerges. This process is repeated, leading to a cascade of period doublings. After multiple period doublings the system finally ascends into chaos. We will be seeing this for logistic maps.

6.3 Logistic Maps

This is an exciting example of a discrete dynamical system. Our equation is given by :-

$$x_{n+1} = rx_n(1 - x_n) \quad (42)$$

Here, x_n represents the population fraction with a time step= n , r is the growth rate parameter, and, $(1 - x_n)$, models resource limitations.

6.3.1 Finding the fixed points and their stability analysis :-

$$x^* = rx^*(1 - x^*) \quad (43)$$

$$x^*(r - rx^* - 1) = 0 \quad (44)$$

gives two solutions,

$$x^* = 0 \quad (45)$$

$$x^* = \frac{r - 1}{r} \quad (46)$$

To find the stability, we compute the derivative:-

$$f'(x) = r(1 - 2x) \quad (47)$$

Evaluating its stability at each fixed point :-

- at $x = 0$, $f'(r) = 0$

- stable if $|r| < 1$. The population dies out.
- unstable if $|r| > 1$. The population continues.
- at $x = \frac{r-1}{r}$, $f'(r) = 2-r$
 - stable if $|2-r| < 1$ and hence we will have; $-1 < r < 3$.
 - unstable if $|r| > 3$. Chaos sets in.

6.3.2 Analysis of Logistics Maps

- In the window, $1 < r < 3$: Here, the population grows steadily and reaches a non zero value.

Figure 18: Time Series plot for $r = 2.8$. [Drive link for the code.](#)

- Now for $r = 3.3$: At $r=3$ and above the fixed point, $x^* = \frac{r-1}{r}$, loses stability. A stable period-two cycle occurs, showing the population oscillates between 2 values.

Figure 19: Time Series plot for $r = 3.3$. [Drive link for the code.](#)

- Now for $r > 3$, more precisely at $r = 3.5$: The period-two cycle becomes unstable, and a period-four cycle emerges. This shows the population repeats every four generations.

Figure 20: Time series plot for $r = 3.5$. [Drive link for the code.](#)

- The period doublings still continue finally and ultimately leading to utter and complete chaos at $r = 3.57$

To better understand the chaotic behavior, we introduce the bifurcation diagram.

Figure 21: Bifurcation diagram of logistic maps. [Drive link for the code.](#)

From fig 21 it is quite clearly visible that the first period doubling happens at nearly $r = 2.8$, followed by the second one at $r = 3.5$. As now r is increased, we see the system enters a state of chaos. The type of bifurcation formed in this case is **pitchfork**

bifurcations. It has been discussed in section 3.4.3. But an intriguing phenomenon is seen at $r = 3.84$.

Figure 22: Periodic window at $r = 3.84$. [Drive link for the code.](#)

This phenomenon is known as periodic windows. At this point for the parameter r , the chaos briefly disappears, and the system slips back into stability. This only happens in chaotic region. The self-similarity in the bifurcation diagram is hard to miss. It is fractal-like, as seen in the bifurcation diagram, especially with the presence of small periodic windows inside the chaotic region.

6.3.3 Chaos and Lyapunov Exponent

As we discussed at $r = 3.57$, our system enters chaos.

- Extreme sensitivity to initial conditions- small changes leads to drastic results.
- We encounter aperiodic behaviour, no repeating cycles.
- Fractal-like structure is seen in the bifurcation diagram.

Lyapunov Exponent

The Lyapunov exponent basically measures where the trajectory diverges and/or converges.

$$\lambda = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \ln |f'(x_n)|$$

where:

- $f(x)$ is the iterative function governing the system,
- $f'(x)$ is its derivative, indicating local stretching or contraction,
- x_n represents the state at step n ,
- N is the number of iterations.

Consider two nearby initial points x_0 and $x_0 + \delta_0$, with a small perturbation δ_0 . The next iterate is:

$$\delta_1 = f(x_0 + \delta_0) - f(x_0) \approx \delta_0 \cdot f'(x_0)$$

Extending this over multiple iterations, we get:

$$\delta_n = \delta_0 \prod_{i=0}^{n-1} |f'(x_i)|$$

The perturbation grows exponentially, following:

$$\delta_n \approx \delta_0 e^{\lambda n}$$

Taking logarithms:

$$\ln \delta_n = \ln \delta_0 + n\lambda$$

Comparing with the product expansion:

$$\lambda = \lim_{N \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{N} \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} \ln |f'(x_n)| \quad (48)$$

Interpretations-

- $\lambda > 0$: System exhibits exponential divergence (chaos).
- $\lambda < 0$: Trajectories converge (stable fixed points).
- $\lambda = 0$: System is at a bifurcation threshold (edge of chaos).

Lyapunov exponent of the logistic map-

Figure 23: Lyapunov exponent of the logistic map. [Drive link for the code.](#)

- When λ is negative, the map is periodic.
- When λ is hitting 0, the map is undergoing bifurcation.
- When $r = 3.0$, $\lambda = 0$, period doubling starts and it starts oscillating.
- When λ is positive, at $r > 3.6$ indicates the chaotic range in this region,

6.4 Feigenbaum's Delta

In the 1970s, using a calculator, Mitchell Feigenbaum discovered that the spacing between the bifurcations shrank in a regular way. This then became a ground-breaking milestone that went on to show that chaos is structured and not random. This delta (δ) is a universal constant, which shows the geometric shrinking of parameter intervals between successive period doubling bifurcations in maps (especially in unimodal maps as discussed in section 6.5) as they approach chaos. Let r_n be the parameter where the first period-2 cycle appears first. Then,

$$\delta = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{r_n - r_{n-1}}{r_{n+1} - r_n} = 4.669 \quad (49)$$

If $\Delta_n = r_n - r_{n+1}$ denotes the difference between the consecutive bifurcation values, then as

$$\frac{\Delta_n}{\Delta_{n+1}} \rightarrow \delta \text{ as } n \rightarrow \infty$$

This δ is a universal constant. This δ shows us the rate at which bifurcations accumulate and shrink. Each new bifurcation appears faster by a factor of δ .

6.5 Universality in Unimodal Maps

What are unimodal maps?

Unimodal maps are one-dimensional maps that have a single peak.

Figure 24: Shape of the unimodal map. [1]

In the case that we have just discussed, the logistic map is a classic example of an unimodal map. Unimodal maps show complete **universality** on the route to chaos despite having extremely different equations. Their bifurcation diagram, Feigenbaums's constant, and self-similarity remain the same. We can hence infer that chaos isn't system-specific; it arises in the simplest of systems and, well quite universally. Extremely simple iterative maps can model chaos exceptionally well. Some examples of unimodal maps are the cubic map and sine map. Let us take a look at them-

- Cubic map: The equation for a cubic map is -

$$x_{n+1} = r x_n (1 - x_n) (1 - \alpha x_n)$$

Figure 25: The bifurcation diagram for the cubic map. [Drive link for the code.](#)

- Sine map: The equation for the sine map is -

$$x_{n+1} = r \sin^2(\pi x_n)$$

Figure 26: The bifurcation diagram for the sine map. [Drive link for the code.](#)

Hence, the similarity in the bifurcation diagrams for the logistic, sine, and cubic maps is

exciting and surprising! The Feigenbaum's delta for the three is also

$$\delta = 4.669$$

This goes on to show the universality in unimodal maps and also goes on to prove yet again that chaos is universal!

7 Gravitational Two Body and Three Body Problems

A lengthy discussion about nonlinear dynamics and their related systems, techniques, and other quantitative tools to understand these systems have been laid out earlier. We now move onto chaotic systems, the gravitational three-body system, and a discussion about its solutions i.e., its fixed points, the Lagrange Points. This is envisaged using a test case of a two-body system which will help in building up to the more complex three-body system.

7.1 Kepler's Laws

In the 17th century, Johannes Kepler gave three laws for planetary motion [3]. The laws were:

1. All planets move in one orbit with the sun at one focus.
2. The line joining a planet to the sun sweeps out equal areas in equal times.
3. If ' T ' is the time period and ' a ' is the semi-major axis of the orbit then, T^2/a^3 , is a constant value; that is it is the same for all planets.

For a 2-body system, it is to be noted that, all three of Kepler's Laws are consequences of the fact that Newton's law of universal gravitation follows an inverse square dependence. This evidently asks what is *Newton's law of universal gravitation*.

Newton's law of universal gravitation states that every body attracts every other body with a force equal to the product of the masses of the two bodies (in this case, m_1 and m_2) and are inversely proportional to the distance between them (here r_{12}). The expression for the force is,

$$F = G \frac{m_1 m_2}{r_{12}^3} r_{12}^{\rightarrow} \quad (50)$$

where G , is the universal gravitation constant,

$$G = 6.67 \times 10^{-11} \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{kg}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}^{-2}. \quad (51)$$

Figure 27: Image for a two-body system, where the Earth is orbiting the Sun, and coordinates for each are specified. The sun is placed at the origin for this coordinate system. [3]

We will now be looking at the two-body system and how we use Kepler's laws and Newton's universal law of gravitation for stability analysis of elliptical orbits and so on.

7.2 Two-Body System and Inverse Square Dependence

Assumptions [3] -

1. The interaction force depends only on the separation 'r'.
2. The relative motion can be treated as a one-body system; that is, the other body is at rest while the second body orbits around it.

Let the masses of the 2 bodies be m_1 and m_2 , respectively. The moving body in this system has a mass equal to the reduced mass, μ . Here,

$$\mu = \frac{m_1 m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \quad (52)$$

The position of the equivalent body, is the relative displacement between the two bodies, and is given by, $\vec{r} = \vec{r}_1 - \vec{r}_2$, where r_1 and r_2 are the displacements of the first and second body respectively. Obviously, if $m_1 \gg m_2$, then μ is approximately equal to m_2 , which is the case when the sun and any other planet is considered.

The orbital trajectory, for a body with mass μ is given by (in polar coordinates) as:-

$$\frac{d^2}{d\theta^2} \left(\frac{1}{r} \right) + \frac{1}{r} = -\frac{\mu \times r^2}{L^2} F(r) \quad (53)$$

where L is the angular momentum given by, $L = \mu r^2 \dot{\theta}$ and $F(r)$ is the force on the body. $F(r) = -G \frac{M_s M_p}{r^2}$. Here, M_s is the mass of the sun and M_p is the mass of the planet. Since $F(r)$ has the inverse square law dependence, hence, eqn 53 can be easily solved. For the sun and another planet (our system), the solution is,

$$\frac{1}{r} = \left(\frac{\mu G M_s M_p}{L^2} \right) [1 - e \cos(\theta + \theta_0)] \quad (54)$$

If we choose $\theta_0 = 0$,

$$r = \left(\frac{L^2}{\mu G M_s M_p} \right) \frac{1}{1 - e \cos \theta} \quad (55)$$

Eqn 55 gives us the result for the shape of the orbital trajectory, which is $r(\theta)$. The eqn 55 represents a conic section. For different values of e , that is, the eccentricity, the trajectories we get are listed below.

- if $e=0$; it is a circle
- if $0 \leq e < 1$; it is a circle
- if $e=1$; it is a parabola
- if $e>1$; it is a hyperbola with a focus at the origin.

Hence, we can clearly conclude that any closed orbit in a two-body system, has an elliptical orbit, as stated from Kepler's 1st law. According to Kepler's 2nd law, we have already used conservation of linear momentum in our calculations. For Kepler's 3rd law, we know the time period T is the ratio between the area enclosed by the elliptical orbit and the rate at which the area is swept out. Hence, $\frac{T^2}{a^3} = \frac{4\pi^2}{[G(M_s + M_p)]} \approx \frac{4\pi^2}{(GM_s)}$. So, we can easily conclude that all three of Kepler's laws follow the inverse square law, which is dependent on Newton's law of universal gravitation.

7.2.1 Inverse Square Dependence

We can carry out some simulations to see whether the gravitational law follows an inverse square dependence [3]. Kepler's laws tell us that, for example, if we have the sun (M_S , denotes the mass of the sun in eqn 56) and another planet (suppose, we take earth, M_E , denotes the mass of the Earth in eqn 56), and that planet has an elliptical orbit, the

orientation of the axes of the elliptical orbit will not change with time. To check for

Figure 28: Hypothetical representation of an elliptical orbit, with the sun lying at one of the foci of the ellipse. Foci are labeled F. [3]

deviations in the gravitational force law following an inverse square dependence-
Let the dependence for the force law be of the form-

$$F_g = \frac{G M_S M_E}{r^\beta} \quad (56)$$

Here, we shall vary β to check for deviations from the original parameter, which is r^2 , the inverse square law dependence, and hence, see how the orientations and behavior of the system changes.

Varying β ::

Note: In all these codes, the initial position of the planet along the horizontal axis x is 0.75 AU (Astronomical Unit) and along the vertical axis y is 0.00 AU. The time step $dt=0.001$ year. We have used the Euler-Cromer method for numerical integration. (References [11] and [12])

Case 1: $\beta = 2$; Inverse square law dependence.

Figure 29: When $\beta = 2$, the inverse square law is followed. The sun is at one of the foci of the ellipse, and the orbit is stable. The orbit is stable in this case. [Drive link for the code.](#)

Case 2: $\beta = 3$, Inverse cube law dependence.

Figure 30: $\beta = 3$ dependence. The planet would not follow a stable orbit in this case. [Drive link for the code.](#)

We make an assumption that as β is made closer to 2, we might get to see a slightly more stable orbit.

Case 3: $\beta = 2.10$

Figure 31: We see even for $\beta = 2.10$, the orbits are not stable and they rotate significantly, although this is an upgrade from the $\beta = 3$ case. [Drive link for the code.](#)

Hence, it is safe to conclude that even slight deviations from the inverse-square dependence cause catastrophic effects. It should also be noted that not just deviations from the inverse square dependence but also the effect of forces from other planets on said planet can cause elliptical orbits to rotate with time. The time for which the orbits remain unstable/ stable depends on the nature of the orbits.

We shall now see what happens when we take into account the effect of other bodies or planets.

7.3 A Celestial Three-Body Problem

Note: The three-body problem can only be solved numerically, and even then, it gives us a highly chaotic system [4].

Let us consider three point masses, m_1 , m_2 , and m_3 with position vectors, \vec{r} , moving under mutual gravitation attraction. This said system has nine degrees of freedom, hence, nine coupled second-order nonlinear ordinary differential equations will determine the dynamics of the system.

$$m_a \frac{d^2 \mathbf{r}_a}{dt^2} = \sum_{b \neq a} G m_a m_b \frac{\mathbf{r}_b - \mathbf{r}_a}{|\mathbf{r}_b - \mathbf{r}_a|^3} \quad \text{for } a = 1, 2, \text{ and } 3. \quad (57)$$

The 3 components of momentum $\mathbf{P} = \sum_a m_a \dot{\mathbf{r}}_a$ and the 3 components of angular momentum, $\mathbf{L} = \sum_a \mathbf{r}_a \times \mathbf{p}_a$ and energy E ,

$$E = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{a=1}^3 m_a \dot{\mathbf{r}}_a^2 - \sum_{a<b} \frac{Gm_a m_b}{|\mathbf{r}_a - \mathbf{r}_b|} \equiv T + V \quad (58)$$

are the seven independent conserved quantities. These seven conserved quantities were used to reduce the Equation of motions.

Jacobi Vectors

Figure 32: $\mathbf{J}_1, \mathbf{J}_2$ and \mathbf{J}_3 are the Jacobi Vectors for the three-body problem, which help us generalise the notion of centre of mass of the particles. [4]

The Jacobi vectors are defined as,

- $\mathbf{J}_1 = \mathbf{r}_2 - \mathbf{r}_1$; is the coordinate of the position vector of mass m_2 relative to m_1 .
- $\mathbf{J}_2 = \mathbf{r}_3 - \frac{m_1 \mathbf{r}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{r}_2}{m_1 + m_2}$; is the coordinate of m_3 relative to the centers of mass m_1 and m_2 .
- $\mathbf{J}_3 = \frac{m_1 \mathbf{r}_1 + m_2 \mathbf{r}_2 + m_3 \mathbf{r}_3}{m_1 + m_2 + m_3}$; is the coordinate of the center of mass.

An interesting feature of jacobi vectors is that their moment of inertia I and kinetic energy K remain diagonal, that is, their off-diagonal elements are 0.

Here, the potential energy V can be expressed completely in terms of \mathbf{J}_1 and \mathbf{J}_2 . Hence V takes the form;

$$V = -\frac{Gm_1 m_2}{|\mathbf{J}_1|} - \frac{Gm_2 m_3}{|\mathbf{J}_2 - \mu_1 \mathbf{J}_1|} - \frac{Gm_3 m_1}{|\mathbf{J}_2 + \mu_2 \mathbf{J}_1|} \text{ where } \mu_{1,2} = \frac{m_{1,2}}{m_1 + m_2} \quad (59)$$

Figure 33: The three bodies are at the vertices of the triangle. [4]

The instantaneous configuration of the three bodies is that of a triangle with the three bodies at the vertices. The moment of inertia about the center of mass gives us the size of the triangle.

$$I_{cm} = M_1 \mathbf{J}_1^2 + M_2 \mathbf{J}_2^2 \quad (60)$$

I_{cm} gives the size of the triangle. It is safe to say when I_{cm} goes to 0, the particles suffer a collision and when I_{cm} goes to infinity, one of the body goes off to infinity.

7.3.1 Example of a three-body system : Earth-Sun-Jupiter

Let us consider the simplest three-body problem to exist, the Sun and two planets orbiting around it [3]. For our case, we shall consider Earth and Jupiter. Our main goal is to understand how the gravitational force of Jupiter affects Earth. We consider Jupiter since its our largest planet. Force between Earth and Jupiter is given by-

$$F = G \frac{M_E M_J}{r_{EJ}^2} \quad (61)$$

where, M_E is the mass of Earth, M_J is the mass of Jupiter and r_{EJ} is the distance between them. We assume the orbits are coplanar and lie along the xy plane.

Figure 34: Positions of Earth(co-ordinates are x_e and y_e) and that of Jupiter (co-ordinates are x_j and y_j). [3]

The total force on Earth in the x- direction would be the sum of the forces from the Sun and Jupiter. Hence, the equation of motion for the x- component of Earth's velocity is,

$$v_{xe}, \quad \frac{dv_{xe}}{dt} = -\frac{GM_S x_e}{r^3} - \frac{GM_J(x_e - x_j)}{r_{EJ}^3} \quad (62)$$

where, r is the distance between the Earth and the Sun. Since $M_s \gg M_E$ or M_J , we consider the Sun to be at rest, with respect to Earth and Jupiter, in a way reducing it to a three-body problem. Let us now look into some simulations regarding these :-

Case 1: We take their masses as they are. Jupiter has a negligible effect on Earth.

Figure 35: Earth + Jupiter system. The sun is considered to be stationary. [Drive link for the code.](#)

Case 2: We take Jupiter's mass ten times its original mass. Jupiter still has a negligible effect on Earth.

Figure 36: Earth + Jupiter system, but Jupiter's mass is 10 times its original mass. [Drive link for the code.](#)

Case 3: We take Jupiter's mass to be a thousand times its original mass. Jupiter is now almost of the same mass as that of the Sun. Earth's orbit now, becomes completely unstable.

Figure 37: Even before Jupiter can finish half an orbit, Earth becomes extremely unstable and chaotic. [Drive link for the code.](#)

Although the sun has been shown in the plot, the effect of Jupiter's increased mass and hence the perturbation caused by it on the sun is ignored and is treated with the sun as a stationary celestial object.

Case 4: Proper three-body simulation, considering the motion and effect of all the three bodies, in consideration here, that is, Earth, Sun and Jupiter.

Figure 38: Shows the chaotic nature of Earth's orbits just as we consider the motion of all three together. Time step taken here = 18 years. [Drive link for the code.](#)

7.4 Restricted Three-Body Problem

A much more simplified version of the three-body problem. Here, one of the masses say, m_3 is considered to be much, much lesser than the other two masses m_1 and m_2 [4]. Hill's Problem (Earth-Sun-Moon) is a famous example of the restricted three-body problem. Satellite launches take the help of the restricted three-body problem for calculations, as the mass of the satellite is much, much less than that of the other planets or celestial bodies in question.

In this planar system, the masses m_1 and m_2 move in circular fixed orbits about their centre of mass with angular speed

$$\omega = (G(m_1 + m_2)/d^3)^{1/2}$$

as given by Kepler's third law. d is the distance between masses m_1 and m_2 . The system has 2 degrees of freedom, and hence has a 4 dimensional phase space, that is its dynamics is governed by 4 coupled second order non-linear ODEs. As discussed before, the Jacobi vectors are the only conserved quantity for this system, which is the energy of m_3 in the co-rotating frame (frame of the primary masses m_1 and m_2). A point to be noted here, is that the origin of the system is at the center of masses of m_1 and m_2 , which coincides with the center of mass of the system as m_3 is much, much lesser than m_1 and m_2 . Here,

we have discussed in plane polar coordinates.

$$E = \frac{1}{2}m_3\dot{r}^2 + \frac{1}{2}m_3r^2\dot{\psi}^2 - \frac{1}{2}m_3\omega^2r^2 - Gm_3\left(\frac{m_1}{r_1} + \frac{m_2}{r_2}\right) = T + V_{\text{eff}} \quad (63)$$

here, r_1 is the distance of m_3 from m_1 and r_2 is the distance between m_3 and m_2 . V_{eff} is the effective potential.

Figure 39: m_3 is present in the co-rotating frames of the m_1 and m_2 . [4]

Although the problem has been developed, we now face the real question, is this even solvable? As we know the three-body problem is not exactly solvable in the closed form. According to Liouville, if a Hamiltonian system with n degrees of freedom is exactly solvable, if and only if, it possesses n independent conserved quantities in involution. Poincaré proved the non-existence of any conserved quantities other than E (*energy*), that is analytic in small mass ratios m_3/m_2 and μ (*reduced mass*). In our case, the only conserved quantity we have is E . Hence, he showed that the restricted three-body problem is not exactly solvable.

This yet again asks the question, what are even the solutions for the restricted three-body problem, and if there are any.

7.5 Lagrange Points

There are 5 equilibrium points that act as solutions to the restricted three-body problem [6]. These points are located near the 2 orbiting masses m_1 and m_2 and are called the **Lagrange Points**.

7.5.1 Finding the Lagrange Points

We want solutions to the equations of motion. The total force exerted on the third mass m_3 by m_1 and m_2 is,

$$\vec{F} = -\frac{Gm_1m_3}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_1|^3}(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_1) - \frac{Gm_2m_3}{|\vec{r} - \vec{r}_2|^3}(\vec{r} - \vec{r}_2) \quad (64)$$

Here, \vec{r}_1 and \vec{r}_2 are both functions of time as m_1 and m_2 are orbiting around each other. We can now look for solutions to the equation of motion, which is:-

$$F(\vec{r}(t)) = m \frac{d^2\vec{r}(t)}{dt^2} \quad (65)$$

The stationary points so obtained are known as the *Lagrange Points*. As we have already stated, to help us reach to the solutions, we need a co-rotating frame of reference in which m_1 and m_2 are fixed. The centre of mass forms the origin of the frame. The angular speed from Kepler's law is, as already discussed is $\omega^2 = (G(m_1 + m_2)/d^3)$. The effective force for this non-inertial frame of reference is F_ω , this force takes into account the centrifugal and coriolis forces as well. We relate the inertial force F from eqn 65 as discussed, with F_ω as ;

$$\vec{F}_\omega = \vec{F} - 2m \left(\vec{\omega} \times \frac{d\vec{r}}{dt} \right) - m\vec{\omega} \times (\vec{\omega} \times \vec{r}) \quad (66)$$

First term is that of the coriolis force and the second of the centrifugal force.

We define a generalised potential to calculate the effective force F_ω . The generalised potential is defined as U_ω .

$$U_\omega = U - \vec{v} \cdot (\vec{\omega} \times \vec{r}) + \frac{1}{2}(\vec{\omega} \times \vec{r}) \cdot (\vec{\omega} \times \vec{r}) \quad (67)$$

We can find the effective force from the generalized gradient as,

$$\vec{F}_\omega = -\nabla_{\vec{r}} U_\omega + \frac{d}{dt}(\nabla_{\vec{v}} U_\omega) \quad (68)$$

The velocity-dependent terms are very important in determining and understanding the dynamic motion and stability near the equilibrium points, although they do not directly affect the position of the equilibrium points.

Figure 40: The contour plot of the generalised potential along with the 5 Lagrange Points. [6]

Finding L_1 , L_2 and L_3

We select cartesian coordinates, with the angular speed aligned with the z axis and the origin at the center of mass of the system. The equations are :-

- $\vec{\omega} = \omega \hat{\mathbf{k}}$
 - $\vec{r} = x(t) \hat{\mathbf{i}} + y(t) \hat{\mathbf{j}}$
 - $\vec{r}_1 = -\alpha R \hat{\mathbf{i}}$
 - $\vec{r}_2 = \beta R \hat{\mathbf{i}}$
- Here, $\alpha = m_2/(m_2 + m_1)$ and $\beta = m_1/(m_2 + m_1)$

Now, let's solve, the equations by levying some conditions on them.

To find the static equilibrium points, we set the velocity $\vec{v} = \frac{d\vec{r}}{dt} = 0$, and try finding solutions to the equations,

$$\vec{F}_\omega = \omega^2 \left(x - \frac{\beta(x + \alpha R)R^3}{((x + \alpha R)^2 + y^2)^{3/2}} - \frac{\alpha(x - \beta R)R^3}{((x - \beta R)^2 + y^2)^{3/2}} \right) \hat{\mathbf{i}} \quad (69)$$

and,

$$\vec{F}_\omega = \omega^2 \left(y - \frac{\beta y R^3}{((x + \alpha R)^2 + y^2)^{3/2}} - \frac{\alpha y R^3}{((x - \beta R)^2 + y^2)^{3/2}} \right) \hat{\mathbf{j}} \quad (70)$$

Mass here, has been chosen to be =1. We now take an analytic approach, cause as is evident, these are very complex equations which when solved will give rise to coupled set of fourteenth order equations.

This system is symmetric about the x-axis, and hence, the y-component of the force must vanish along the x-line. Using this condition and hence solving, we arrive at three fifth-order coupled equations. Numerically solving these would still be quite a task. Hence, we solve them analytically. We take α to be of the lowest order possible for the mass ratio. Taking this approximation into account and considering the roots of the quintic equation, we arrive at the location for the first three Lagrange points. The first three Lagrange points are positioned at

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\bullet L_1 = \left(R \left(1 - \frac{\alpha^{1/3}}{3} \right), 0 \right) \\
 &\bullet L_2 = \left(R \left(1 + \frac{\alpha^{1/3}}{3} \right), 0 \right) \\
 &\bullet L_3 = \left(-R \left(1 + \frac{5}{12}\alpha \right), 0 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Now, the values of α and R depend on the system in consideration and hence, we can determine the positions. For example for the Earth-Sun system, $\alpha = 3 \times 10^{-6}$ and $R = 1AU = 1.5 \times 10^8$ km, L_1 and L_2 are located approximately 1.5 million kilometers from Earth. L_3 orbits around the sun.

Finding L_4 and L_5

This is a bit tricky to find. We need some force to balance the centrifugal force, which acts radially outwards from the center of the mass, while also accounting for the gravitational force being exerted between the two masses [5].

Figure 41: Forces being balanced to calculate L_4 and L_5 . [5]

From the fig , we can clearly see that the centrifugal force depends on \vec{r} , hence, balancing the forces would only include the gravitational force, which would be perpendicular to \vec{r} .

$$F_{per} = \alpha\beta\omega^2 R^3 \left(\frac{1}{[(x - R\beta)^2 + y^2]^{3/2}} - \frac{1}{[(x + R\alpha)^2 + y^2]^{3/2}} \right) = 0 \quad (71)$$

On solving, we get, $x = \frac{1}{2}(\beta R - \alpha R)$. This is quite interesting because if a Lagrange point does exist, it will be located exactly half way between the 2 masses! Now, the equations are somewhat reduced, and by substituting and we finally find the parallel component, which is,

$$F_{par} = \omega^2 \frac{x^2 + y^2}{R} \left(\frac{1}{R^3} - \frac{1}{((x - R\beta)^2 + y^2)^{3/2}} \right) \quad (72)$$

Now, we see that the equation equates distance between the points in terms of R . We can now conclude that the Lagrange point is at a distance R from m_1 and, hence, from m_2 . L_4 is at the vertex of the equilateral triangle and L_5 is obtained as L_4 's mirror image. We can now conclude that, the remaining 2 Lagrange points are positioned at :-

- $L_4 = \left(\frac{R}{2} \left(\frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \right), \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} R \right)$
- $L_5 = \left(\frac{R}{2} \left(\frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \right), -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2} R \right)$

Finally, we can conclude that the 5 Lagrange Points are positioned at:

- $L_1 = \left(R \left(1 - \frac{\alpha^{1/3}}{3} \right), 0 \right)$
- $L_2 = \left(R \left(1 + \frac{\alpha^{1/3}}{3} \right), 0 \right)$
- $L_3 = \left(-R \left(1 + \frac{5}{12}\alpha \right), 0 \right)$
- $L_4 = \left(\frac{R}{2} \left(\frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \right), \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \right)$
- $L_5 = \left(\frac{R}{2} \left(\frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1 + m_2} \right), -\frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}R \right)$

Here, R , m_1 , m_2 , α all depend on the specific system under consideration.

L_1 , L_2 , L_3 are all located at saddle points and hence are rather unstable. L_4 and L_5 are located at the maxima, the two vertices of the equilateral triangle. Here is a plot to show roughly the positions of the Lagrange points without any effective potential contours.

Figure 42: The 5 Lagrange Points. [Drive link for the code.](#)

7.5.2 Some Notes on Lagrange Points

Figure 43: The 5 Lagrange Points for the Earth-Sun System. [13]

- **L₁: Lagrange Point 1:** This point, as is evident from fig 43, lies on the line between the the 2 masses m_1 and m_2 . The gravitational pull between the two masses creates an equilibrium point here. For the Sun-Earth system, any object placed at L_1 , their orbital period becomes approximately equal to that of Earth's. ISRO's Aditya L1 satellite is placed in halo orbit around the L_1 point in the Earth-Sun System.
- **L₂: Lagrange Point 2:** This point lies beyond the second mass; refer to fig 43 and in most cases this second mass is less heavier than the first mass. Hence, the combined gravitational forces balance off the centrifugal force that the body feels at that point, and hence, we find an equilibrium point. The James Webb Telescope orbits around L_2 . Earlier, Wilkinson Microwave Anisotropy Probe was present there.
- **L₃: Lagrange Point 3:** The hidden point, fig 43. This point is placed behind the Sun for the Earth-Sun system, i.e., it is in line with the two masses and is placed behind the heavier mass. This point orbits around the barycenter of the Sun-Earth system. No known celestial objects are found there, and neither is any satellite placed there due to its extreme instability because of the gravitational forces involved there. Even though this point cannot be used by scientists, science fiction authors and movies have surely had their fun with it as this is the location of Planet X.

- **L₄ and L₅: Lagrange Points 4 and 5:** Refer to fig 43. If an equilateral triangle is constructed keeping the two masses as the two vertices, the third vertex would be either of these two points. The Trojan Asteroids are found to orbit around these two points. These points owe their stability to the coriolis force. Further discussion is provided in the next section.

7.5.3 Stability Analysis of the Five Lagrange Points

Figure 44: Contour plot to understand stability of the 5 Lagrange points. [Link for image.](#)

Stability analysis of the Lagrange points is our next point of discussion. Since these points are used extensively by physicists for the stationing of satellites and the analysis of astrodynamics, they are all dependent on the stability of these points. It is quite easy to determine the stability of the Lagrange points just by looking at the iso-potential contours [6]. The location of these points at the valleys, saddles, hills in contours, give us an idea, but they aren't very accurate. We must perform a linear stability analysis through each of these Lagrange points.

We begin doing this by linearising the equation of motion about each equilibrium solution and solving for the departures from the equilibrium.

The equation of motions now become,

$$x = x_i + \delta x, \quad v_x = \delta v_x \quad (73)$$

$$y = y_i + \delta y, \quad v_y = \delta v_y \quad (74)$$

where, x_i and y_i is the position of the i – th Lagrangian points.

The linearised equations of motion now are :-

$$\frac{d}{dt} \begin{pmatrix} \delta x \\ \delta y \\ \delta v_x \\ \delta v_y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 1 \\ \frac{d^2 U_\omega}{dx^2} & \frac{d^2 U_\omega}{dx dy} & 0 & 2\omega \\ \frac{d^2 U_\omega}{dy dx} & \frac{d^2 U_\omega}{dy^2} & -2\omega & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} \delta x \\ \delta y \\ \delta v_x \\ \delta v_y \end{pmatrix} \quad (75)$$

Here, the second derivatives of U_ω are evaluated at $\vec{r} = (x_i, y_i)$.

Stability of L_1 and L_2 Points

Let us look at the contour of the points near L_1 and L_2 . From fig 7.5.3, we can see that L_1 and L_2 both are saddle points, as indicated by the curvature of the effective potential. Hence, the equation of curvature becomes :-

$$\frac{d^2 U_\omega}{dx^2} = \mp 9\omega^2, \quad \frac{d^2 U_\omega}{dy^2} = \pm 3\omega^2, \quad \frac{d^2 U_\omega}{dx dy} = \frac{d^2 U_\omega}{dy dx} = 0 \quad (76)$$

Solving for the eigenvalues from the linearisation matrix, we get

$$\lambda_{\pm} = \pm \omega \sqrt{1 + 2\sqrt{7}} \quad (77)$$

and

$$\sigma_{\pm} = \pm i\omega \sqrt{2\sqrt{7} - 1} \quad (78)$$

from eqn 77 and eqn 78, it is clear that we have positive and real roots, which makes L_1 and L_2 dynamically unstable. Small deviations from the equilibrium will grow quite largely.

Let us look more for precise time when due to some disturbance or perturbation the instability seeps in and starts growing. For this we include the concept of **e-time**. **e-time**, also known as e-folding time, refers to the timescale over which small perturbations in the system grow exponentially by the Euler number e , due to instability. In simple

words, it tells us that if any disturbance occurs at that point, how fast can something go wrong there. It is denoted as t_e and is defined as, $t_e = 1/\lambda$ for Lagrange points.

For L_1 and L_2 , we observe that the e-folding time is very less. The e-folding time is, $t_e = 1/\lambda = 2/5 \omega$. For Sun-Earth system, the $\omega = 2\pi$ ($year^{-1}$), hence $t_e = 23$ days.

So for satellites placed in L_1 and L_2 , if corrections are not made in due time, after 23 days, they will wander off.

Stability of L_3 Point

From fig 7.5.3, it is clear that L_3 is a very weak saddle point. The equation of the curvature becomes:-

$$\frac{d^2U_\omega}{dx^2} = -3\omega^2, \quad \frac{d^2U_\omega}{dy^2} = \frac{7m_2}{8m_1}\omega^2, \quad \frac{d^2U_\omega}{dxdy} = \frac{d^2U_\omega}{dydx} = 0 \quad (79)$$

Now, the eigenvalues from the linearised matrix, i.e., from eqn75, are-

$$\lambda_{\pm} = \pm \sqrt{\frac{3m_1}{8m_2}} \quad (80)$$

and,

$$\sigma_{\pm} = \pm i\sigma\sqrt{7} \quad (81)$$

We see yet again that we have, real positive roots, indicating instability. For the Sun-Earth system, the e-time in this case, $t_e = 1/\lambda = 150$ years. The long e-time does make L_3 a good parking spot.

Note: Even though t_e for L_3 is much much greater than that for L_2 or L_1 , it is still not a preferred point as, even after being nudged away from this point, the object will drift away and not oscillate about that point, like it does in case of L_4 and L_5 . Even though the drift is slow for L_3 , it is inevitable. The exponential decay is slow due to large t_e , but it is very much present. Even if an object drifts away from that point, it will never return to that point, even if it takes 150 years to drift away completely!

Stability of L_4 and L_5 Points

From fig 7.5.3, we see that these points are the local maxima for the generalized potential, which indicates a state of unstable equilibrium. But, these points owe their stability to the coriolis force. Initially, any object situated at these points would slide down, and as it does, it starts picking up speed; hence, coriolis force kicks in here sending that object orbiting around the points. This is analogous to how typhoons are formed on Earth.

The equation of the curvature of the potential is given by,

$$\frac{d^2U_\omega}{dx^2} = \frac{3}{4}\omega^2, \quad \frac{d^2U_\omega}{dy^2} = \frac{9}{4}\omega^2, \quad \frac{d^2U_\omega}{dxdy} = \frac{d^2U_\omega}{dydx} = \frac{3\sqrt{3}}{4}\kappa\omega^2 \quad (82)$$

here, $\kappa = \frac{m_1 - m_2}{m_1 + m_2}$. The eigenvalues from the linearized matrix, i.e., from eqn 75, are-

$$\lambda_{\pm} = \pm i \frac{\omega}{2} \sqrt{2 - \sqrt{27\kappa - 23}} \quad (83)$$

and,

$$\sigma_{\pm} = \pm i \frac{\omega}{2} \sqrt{2 + \sqrt{27\kappa - 23}} \quad (84)$$

The points are only stable when the eigenvalues are purely imaginary. This will be true if we have,

$$\kappa^2 \geq \frac{23}{27} \text{ and } \sqrt{27\kappa - 23} \leq 2 \quad (85)$$

The second condition is almost always fulfilled. For the first condition to be fulfilled, we have an intermediate condition that is related to the mass ratio. It is,

$$m_1 \geq 25 m_2 \left(\frac{1 + \sqrt{1 - 4/265}}{2} \right) \quad (86)$$

And since the point L_5 is just a mirror image of L_4 , the values used are the same with the signs inverted. When L_4 and L_5 yield stable points, they become places for Trojan asteroids. The mass-ratio for the Sun-Earth and Sun-Jupiter systems is large enough to become home to the Trojan asteroids.

To summarise the stability analysis:-

- L_1, L_2, L_3 , the collinear points are highly unstable.
- L_4 and L_5 the hilltops are highly stable points.

8 Conclusion

This dissertation has investigated the complex dynamics of non-linear systems, connecting theoretical analysis with computational understanding in discrete and continuous frameworks. Starting with basic concepts in non-linear dynamics, we analyzed the dynamics of one-dimensional continuous systems using fixed points, linear stability, and bifurcations. The logistic map provided a paradigmatic model of discrete chaos with period-doubling sequences to chaos, fractal-like bifurcation diagrams, and the crucial role of Lyapunov exponents in measuring sensitivity to initial conditions. Cobweb diagrams and time-series plots distinguished the behavior moving from stability to chaos, emphasizing the ability of simple iterative equations to represent complex phenomena such as population dynamics.

In gravitational systems, we moved on to the three-body problem, a foundation of celestial mechanics. Through the study of the restricted three-body problem, we obtained the five Lagrange points, equilibrium solutions paramount in satellite positioning and the determination of orbital stability. Linear stability analysis showed that L_1 , L_2 , L_3 , the collinear points, are highly unstable. L_4 and L_5 , the hilltops are highly stable points and are stabilized by the Coriolis force, having Trojan asteroids in Sun-Jupiter-type systems. Numerical simulation showed how departures from inverse-square gravitational laws or perturbations caused by large bodies (e.g., Jupiter) trigger chaotic orbital motion, highlighting the instability of multi-body systems.

The combination of Poincaré maps and Jacobi vectors offered means to represent chaotic trajectories in models such as Hénon-Heiles model and Lorenz attractor, thus testifying to chaos ubiquity in both astrophysics and fluid dynamics. These tools not only decipher complicated systems but also provide predictive schemes for practical uses, ranging from weather prediction to spacecraft trajectory planning.

The concepts developed here are applied to sophisticated astrophysical phenomena, including accretion disc dynamics [23], black hole collisions [24], and exoplanetary systems [25]. Subsequent research might apply analogous non-linear methods to the investigation of gravitational waves [26], dark matter distributions [27], or quantum chaos [28]. By combining analytical rigor with computational power, this dissertation reveals how non-linear dynamics unravel the universe's ordered yet unpredictable fabric.

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